

tilburg.ai

Annual Report
2024-2025

16 April 2025

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This report is available open access at:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15231645>

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Management Summary

This is the first annual report of Tilburg.ai, a project dedicated to the **responsible development and use of AI in education at Tilburg University**. Backed by €360,000 in funding from the Tilburg School of Economics and Management (TiSEM) over a two-year period (starting March 2024), we have focused on four key activities in our first year:

- Our **website** (<https://tilburg.ai>) features over 75 articles on generative AI in education, from tutorials and prompting guides to implementation tips. In 2024, the site drew more than 116,000 global visits. On social media, our posts reached over 66,000 views, raising Tilburg University's visibility and attracting collaboration requests from national and international partners.
- To **build AI literacy**, we delivered over 30 hands-on workshops and presentations across schools, departments, and divisions, in collaboration with the Teaching & Learning Center (TLC). We also supported the central working group on AI in education in launching two e-learning modules: one for students (<https://student.tilburg.ai>, also available on Canvas) and one for staff (<https://learn.tilburg.ai>).
- As an **R&D lab**, we focused on developing AI tools to improve education. Our course chatbot, piloted in 25 courses, helps students get citable, course-based answers to questions. We built a self-service platform for teachers to create their own bots and share them with students, a presentation-to-video converter that turns slides into web clips, and a prototype bot that can potentially assess students through oral conversation. Importantly, we have laid the foundation for building and scaling educational apps made at Tilburg University.
- Finally, we have worked closely with IT and policy staff at Tilburg University to **align IT infrastructure and regulations with educational needs**. To ensure long-term availability and compliance with data protection standards, we have recently secured formal approval to migrate tilburg.ai's computational infrastructure to university IT.

Our project is supported by growing external recognition. We contributed to the Erasmus+ FLAIR grant for AI literacy (funded) and play a central role in two major proposals in the final selection stages: a €500,000 Comenius Leadership grant (NRO) focused on student-led app development, and a €1.5 million Open Science Infrastructure grant (OpenScience NL/NWO) to support reproducible research.

To sustain our momentum in responsibly integrating AI in education, we propose embedding tilburg.ai permanently at Tilburg University—with funding beyond the initial term, a dedicated team, and clear governance.

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1 Introduction

1.1 TiSEM's investment in AI

In March 2023, Tilburg School of Economics and Management (TiSEM) launched a working group focused on AI in education. The working group held regular meetings from March 2023 to February 2024, led by TiSEM's vice dean for education, prof. dr. Herbert Hamers. As part of the working group, the website tilburg.ai was launched to inform students and faculty about AI's role in education.

Since November 2023, two student assistants at TiSEM regularly created content for the website, under the guidance of dr. Hannes Datta. In addition, an accompanying social media presence on LinkedIn and Instagram was launched to promote the website among the target audience. The website's content (e.g., "how to use ChatGPT for prompting in education") was discussed on multiple occasions with stakeholders at Tilburg University, including the vice deans of education from all schools, as well as the Executive Board.

Given the systemic impact that artificial intelligence (AI) is expected to have on the educational sector¹, the management team (MT) of TiSEM decided to expand its support of tilburg.ai with an investment of €360,000 over a two-year period, starting in March 2024. A key component of this initiative was to hire a lecturer who would work closely with TiSEM departments to provide workshops and accelerate the dissemination of AI-driven innovations. In addition to funding a full-time staff member, the budget also covered material costs for developing AI applications, compensation for the time Hannes Datta dedicated to the project, and resources for exploring AI tools and subscriptions relevant to education.

Concurrent with the two-year funding of tilburg.ai, a working group on AI in education was established under the leadership of Hannes Datta at the central level (i.e., for Tilburg University, not just TiSEM). This group includes support staff, teachers, and researchers from TSHD, TiSEM, TSB, TLS, and TUNEDIN, ensuring cross-disciplinary collaboration and alignment with university-wide educational goals, as laid out in the Long-Term Memo LLMs/Gen AI of Tilburg University.²

The central working group for AI in education frequently discussed tilburg.ai, with useful insights exchanged among its members. While this annual report primarily focuses on tilburg.ai, some overlap with the working group naturally occurs and is reflected in this

¹ Ministerie van Algemene Zaken. Government-wide vision on generative AI of the Netherlands. Parliamentary Document (available at <https://www.government.nl/documents/parliamentary-documents/2024/01/17/government-wide-vision-on-generative-ai-of-the-netherlands>).

² In particular, the working group focused on "creating innovative learning models and assessment methods that prepare students for a future where GenAI is an integral part of everyday life."

report—for instance, when our team handled technical implementation and the working group provided substantive input.

1.2 Project goals

As per Figure 1, the goals of *tilburg.ai* were defined along four key pillars: (1) website (available at <https://tilburg.ai>), (2) workshops for faculty, (3) AI lab / R&D, and (4) policy and infrastructure recommendations. The arrows in the figure illustrate the interaction between these pillars. For example, insights gained during workshops (2) could inform updates to the website (1), while developments in the lab (3) may feed into institutional policy and infrastructure recommendations (4).

Figure 1: The four key pillars of *tilburg.ai*, as commissioned by TiSEM’s MT for the project period March 2024-February 2026.

Specific project goals, for each of the four pillars, are shown in Table 1.

Pillar 1: Website (<i>tilburg.ai</i>)	Pillar 2: Workshops
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grow the website to be actively used in all of TiSEM’s educational programs • Build a community of student volunteers and paid research assistants to curate and edit content. • Involve expert faculty members to contribute insights on educational case studies or AI technology in general (or invite from other schools/universities, such as via TAISIG) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give workshops to faculty members and TiSEM support staff (e.g., on effective search, prompt engineering) • Develop and launch a self-guided Canvas course for faculty members (e.g., similar to the privacy & security course recently completed by TiU faculty) • Develop and launch a self-guided “AI-ready course” for TiSEM students, explaining the ins and outs of ChatGPT and other tools

Pillar 3: Lab / R&D	Pillar 4: Policy and infrastructure recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop new AI tools to realize efficiency gains at TiSEM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Automated grading & validation ○ Individualizing course assignments (development and grading support) ○ Chatbot about course syllabi and program guidelines ○ Build ChatUVT – finding information on our intranet ○ Develop course catalog and “hand over” to TiU (e.g., marketing & communication) ○ Build an interactive tool with “default prompts” that can be used at Tilburg ● Test existing AI tools and devise small-scale pilots with selected departments/courses/programs at TiSEM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Involve all TiSEM departments in this project (e.g., workshops and course content to be developed for all departments) ● Closely coordinate our initiative with TiU-wide initiatives (e.g., TunedIn) ● Incorporate in TiSEM’s educational programs ● Gain support of marketing and communication and academic services (AS)

Table 1: Project goals, for each of the four pillars of tilburg.ai

1.3 Key results

This annual report covers the first year of tilburg.ai (mid-March 2024–mid-March 2025). Below, we summarize the main highlights that shaped our work—ranging from building a practical website and delivering workshops and trainings, to developing applied AI tools and contributing to university policy on AI.

In the following sections, we offer a detailed reflection and systematic assessment of our progress over the past year across the four key pillars.

Key highlights in our first year were:

- **Website Growth:** We transformed our website—tilburg.ai—into a popular blog with more than 75 articles, from how-to guides and tutorials to ethical considerations around AI – all with an educational focus. The site grew from 678 monthly users in February 2024 to 8,000 monthly visitors by March 2025, reaching a total of 116,209 page views by the end of 2024.
- **Publishing E-learning Module on Responsible AI Use:** In collaboration with the working group for AI in education, we adapted and launched a university-wide e-module initially developed at UvA on the responsible use of generative AI. Next to a version for teachers (<https://learn.tilburg.ai>), a student version is available both on our website (<https://student.tilburg.ai>) and on Canvas (which can be easily imported by teachers into their program or course pages). To comply with the AI Act, which requires that anyone using or managing AI systems has a basic understanding of how they work (European Union, 2024), this e-learning module will be mandatory for both students and staff as the first step toward AI literacy.

- **Workshops & Talks:** Via the working group for AI in education, we catalogized workshop material available at various schools (e.g., TSB) and divisions (e.g., AS via TLC). Collectively, we gave 30+ workshops and talks to academic staff, support teams, and students. Topics ranged from ChatGPT in teaching to AI in assessment. Formally, we handed over the provision of workshops to TLC. In addition, we have been invited to present the activities of tilburg.ai at other Universities (e.g., TU/e, Fontys via Mindlabs, RUG, UvA).
- **Course Chatbot:** We developed and tested a course chatbot, piloted in 25 courses across multiple schools. It allows students to ask questions based on course materials and receive answers with cited references. After a successful pilot, the team added key features such as SSO login, chat memory, Canvas integration, and a backend for teachers to easily create their own chatbots.

Following a decision by the POW in October 2024, and in collaboration with the Information Manager at TUNEDIN, LIS was responsible for delivering the required infrastructure by Q1 2025. This will enable the migration from tilburg.ai's current Azure environment to the university's own, ensuring better compliance and cost savings through existing contracts. As the migration has not yet started, the chatbot has not been rolled out to students at scale.

- **PowerPoint-to-Video Tool:** We developed a tool that generates web clips from presentation slides using AI-generated speech. This allows teachers to quickly update their web clips by simply modifying a slide—making it easy to keep course content current from year to year. In addition to short clips, the tool can also be used to create full-length lectures, offering a flexible and time-saving solution for digital course delivery. We are currently in the process of soliciting feedback and exploring funding options, as professional-grade AI voice services incur costs that make it unfeasible to offer the tool to all instructors at Tilburg University without additional support.
- **Early Prototypes:** In addition to tools that are ready for rollout—pending the necessary IT infrastructure from Tilburg University—we have also invested in developing early prototypes of AI-driven educational applications. For example, we created a demo of an AI bot capable of conducting oral assessments. The bot can ask clarification questions, is designed with safeguards to steer conversations back to exam content if they stray and generates transcripts for grading. We are also exploring alternative applications of this technology in educational settings.
- **Policy & Grants:** We contributed to drafting university guidelines on responsible AI use in education, especially around assignments and assessment. We also secured an Erasmus+ FLAIR grant (±50k EUR) to create modules about AI literacy

across European universities. We are currently in the final decision stages for a Comenius Leadership Grant (Hannes Datta; expansion of tilburg.ai and IT infrastructure to allow students to develop AI-driven apps; 500k EUR), and an Open Science Infrastructure Grant (Hannes Datta, together with Ana Martinovici (Erasmus) and Tom Emery (ODISSEI); if granted, tilburg.ai will develop an AI bot to support researchers in creating replication packages for their research projects; 1.5 million EUR). Finally, we have been contacted by Tilburg University faculty to inquire about including us in other grant proposals.

1.4 Current team

In March 2024, the team of tilburg.ai consisted of three research assistants (RAs) focused solely on writing content for the website. By March 2025, our team has been expanded to five RAs, bringing in the necessary technical expertise to develop and deploy our own AI applications. Team members came from various master’s programs, including Data Science & Society (TSHD), Data Science (JADS), and AI & Data Science (TU Eindhoven). Additionally, one RA was brought on to manage our social media presence, significantly increasing our reach on LinkedIn, Instagram, and the website. Throughout this period, Matthijs van Gils increasingly took on the role of product manager for the developer pool, serving as a key link between teaching staff, researchers, and members of the support organization. Hannes represented tilburg.ai both within and beyond Tilburg University, advising Matthijs and channeling ideas from the Tilburg community to support the development and testing of new initiatives.

Table 2: Team members at tilburg.ai (March 2025)

We believe that our team has been a great example of what can be achieved by hiring talented master’s students and providing them with the freedom, guidance, and

opportunities to explore their creativity and develop their skills. One of our RAs successfully graduated during the year and is now employed full-time in a technical role at *Techonomy*. This summer, three more RAs will leave our team to start their careers in the field of AI, equipped with highly valued experience in developing and deploying AI apps in this project.

2 Website (tilburg.ai)

In 2024, Tilburg.ai continued to grow as a go-to platform for exploring and applying Generative AI (GenAI) in academia. Our mission remained the same: helping students and faculty adopt GenAI in a responsible and informed way. In Figure 2, we depict a screenshot of the landing page, captured in March 2025.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the homepage of tilburg.ai (March 2025).

2.1 Content development

By the end of the year, our platform had grown substantially, expanding from 20 articles at the end of 2023 to 75. Given the rapid pace of AI developments, we introduced a systematic content review process to keep information current and relevant. Our scope also broadened beyond educational AI tools to cover a range of learning goals.

To improve accessibility, we organized content into categories. These include technical tutorials and informational pieces. We also invite experts to contribute articles, sharing their perspectives on emerging AI trends and developments. Some exemplary articles from our website are:

- A privacy guide for ChatGPT, alongside scholarly introductions to AI safety and alignment principles.
- A prompt engineering series offering conceptual explanations, practical examples, and skill-building exercises to help users interact effectively with GenAI.
- Technical documentation on API implementation and integration for more advanced users.
- A LibGuides partnership, providing a tutorial on proper citation methods for AI-generated content.

Each article is labeled according to its difficulty level—beginner, intermediate, or advanced—so readers can easily find content that matches their expertise. While most articles are relevant for both students and teachers, some are also exclusively focused on one of these two target groups. Across all content, we seek to maintain a focus on ethical considerations, addressing issues such as algorithmic bias and promoting responsible AI adoption in academic settings.

In Figure 3, we show the most read articles so far at tilburg.ai, illustrating the diversity of content.

Figure 3: The most read articles at tilburg.ai (cumulative by March 2025; top 10 shown).

In addition to this educational content, tilburg.ai also acts as a central “access point” for self-developed AI tools. Finally, through the website, we highlight AI-related events of the Teaching & Learning Centre (TLC) for university employees.

2.2 Website Reach

The development of the content portfolio has driven significant growth in platform engagement throughout 2024. From a modest beginning of 678 unique users in February 2024, we recorded 8,000 unique visitors by October 2024, representing an eleven-fold increase. These figures exclude interactions with the e-modules and course chatbot, which we tracked separately.

User engagement has been distributed across our content, with 68 distinct pages each attracting over 100 unique visitors, highlighting broad interest. In total, the website generated 116,209 page views during the 2024 calendar year.

Figure 4: Active users of tilburg.ai, between January 2024 and December 2024.

Our analytics show that most visitors find our platform through organic search (49,541 visits), highlighting our strong visibility and relevance in the GenAI space—thanks to high rankings on search engines like Google. Direct traffic, including visits from social media referrals, accounts for another significant portion (41,375 visits). Additional traffic comes from referrals (2,758), organic social media (869), and email (269).

In terms of reach, Tilburg.ai gained recognition from both national and international academic institutions over the past year, with referrals from universities such as the University of Groningen and the University of Stavanger. Our content is also regularly cited by media outlets and educational blogs, including *Univers Magazine* and *Vernieuwingderwijs*.

2.3 Social Media

In addition to expanding our website, we also grew our presence on social media. This year, we brought Francisco Ruete on board as a research assistant fully dedicated to creating content for our social channels. Social media has proven to be a great way to showcase our work, share updates, and highlight our achievements as a project.

Our LinkedIn activity over the past year offers a clear snapshot of our project’s progress. We shared podcasts (e.g., via TAISIG)³, interviews (e.g., with CEO PriceWaterHouseCoopers Belgium)⁴, and event highlights, as well as showcased the AI tools we developed and articles we published. Some posts reached a broad audience—for instance, after sharing about our chatbot on social media, we were invited by the University of Groningen, the University of Amsterdam, and TU Eindhoven to discuss implementing similar tools. Through these efforts, we aim to contribute to Tilburg University’s reputation as a leader in AI innovation in education.

As a result of our consistent social media activity, our LinkedIn posts now have reached over 66,000 impressions, and our follower count grew to nearly 700—a strong foundation for further engagement and outreach. We provide an impression of our LinkedIn activity in Figure 5.

Follower demographics ⓘ

Highlights

Data for 3/20/2024 - 3/19/2025

66,710
Impressions

1,538
Reactions

Visitor demographics ⓘ

Figure 5: LinkedIn Activity for tilburg.ai.

³ E.g., via TAISIG Talks (<https://www.tilburguniversity.edu/nl/onderzoek/instituten-en-researchgroepen/taisig/taisig-talks/taisig-talks-podcast-ai-tools-het-onderwijs>),

⁴ E.g., Hannes Datta, interviewed by CEO PriceWaterhouseCoopers Belgium, in their “AI Unscripted” interview series, available at <https://www.pwc.be/en/news-publications/podcasts/ai-unscripted.html>.

3 Workshops and Training

A core part of tilburg.ai’s goals is to build AI literacy among educators and learners. To accomplish this, our team organized various workshops, training sessions, and presentations. We focused on showing how AI can be used in real teaching situations and encouraged staff and students to try things out in a responsible, hands-on way.

3.1 Talks and Workshops for University Staff

Hannes Datta and Matthijs van Gils gave numerous talks and workshops to different university teams, including the secretariat, KTO, Grant Support, academic directors at TiSEM, and during TUNEDIN’s Academic Director Day. These sessions helped staff understand how AI can support their daily work and stimulated thinking about responsible innovation. For a list of talks and workshops, see Table 3.

Date	Event	Speakers
09 April 2024	Academic Director Day: Student engagement and working with AI	Matthijs van Gils
18 April 2024	Presentation Tilburg.ai at PIT (Mindlabs)	Matthijs van Gils
30 April 2024	Interview Tilburg.ai & Working Group for Tilburg University website	Matthijs & Nadia Klein
23 May 2024	Talk at Program Directors Event	Matthijs van Gils & Hannes Datta
23 May 2024	TAISIG Podcast	Matthijs van Gils & Hannes Datta
25 May 2024	Talk at TUNEDIN Network Event	Hannes Datta
02 June 2024	Workshop for all secretaries of TiSEM	Matthijs van Gils & Hannes Datta
03 Sept 2024	Guest Lecture at “Marketing in bedrijf”	Matthijs van Gils
09 Oct 2024	Guest Lecture at Master Marketing Management	Matthijs van Gils
17 Oct 2024	Presentation at TU Eindhoven	Matthijs van Gils & Hannes Datta
21 Oct 2024	Presentation for Czech University Guests	Matthijs van Gils
28 Oct 2024	Presentation Tilburg.ai at Groningen University	Matthijs van Gils
19 Nov 2024	Presentation Tilburg.ai at Teaching & Learning Center (TLC)	Matthijs van Gils
21 Nov 2024	Second Presentation at TLC	Matthijs van Gils
14 Jan 2025	Workshop for KTO/Grant Support	Matthijs van Gils
16 Jan 2025	Follow-up Workshop for KTO/Grant Support	Matthijs van Gils
28 Jan 2025	Mindlabs Presentation with Avans & Tilburg.ai	Matthijs van Gils
03 Feb 2025	Podcast at PWC Belgium	Hannes Datta
12 Feb 2025	Talk at Economics Department, TiSEM	Hannes Datta
13 Feb 2025	SURF x Tilburg.ai Presentation	Matthijs van Gils & Team

Table 3: Overview of workshops & presentations

3.2 AI Workshops for teachers, researchers, and PhD Students

In collaboration with TLC, represented by the central working group member Nikos Basbas, hands-on AI workshops were organized for lecturers and PhD candidates throughout the academic year. These sessions offered a practical, accessible introduction to AI tools and their potential applications in education while also creating space to reflect on the opportunities and challenges AI presents for teaching and learning.

A total of seven workshops were already given, and there already many more planned.⁵ Each workshop was given for about 10-15 participants. Feedback from attendees was positive, with many reporting increased confidence in navigating the AI landscape and new ideas for integrating AI into their own teaching practices.

In addition to the collaboration with TLC, tilburg.ai will contribute to a new series of AI-focused workshops in May 2025, organized by Tilburg University's research infrastructure team. These sessions will also be recorded to ensure continued accessibility across the academic community.

3.3 E-learning Module for Students and Faculty Members

An important addition this year was the adoption and implementation of two e-modules on the responsible use of GenAI, originally created by the University of Amsterdam and adapted for Tilburg University. [Tilburg.ai](https://tilburg.ai) provided technical support to host the modules and promote them via their social media channels.

For teachers, researchers and staff, the module is accessible at learn.tilburg.ai. For students, an adapted version is accessible at student.tilburg.ai and fully integrated into Canvas, allowing teachers to include it as a mandatory part of their courses (easily downloadable via Commons). In Figure 6, we show a screenshot of the module, as shown at student.tilburg.ai.

The POW has recently decided to make this e-learning module mandatory to ensure that Tilburg University complies with the AI Act, which requires AI literacy for anyone using AI tools in education or business. This is an important first step toward AI literacy at our university. We are proud to have successfully delivered this module together with the working group for AI in education.

⁵ Workshops, under the leadership of TLC, will be held on the following dates: April 9, April 23, May 7 and June 11. For more info check out the [Calendar TLC academy](#)

Welcome to this e-module on Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI)!

This e-module is aimed at students who want to learn more about the responsible use of ChatGPT and GenAI in higher education.

Please note that Tilburg University is currently working on establishing AI policy, and therefore the contents of this e-module are to be considered guidelines. Nevertheless, a "positive inclusion approach" has been adopted, whereby in some courses the use of GenAI tools is allowed, whereas in others it is not. Check course guidelines and instructions from your lecturers or supervisors on a case-by-case basis. Furthermore, it is good to educate yourself on how ChatGPT and GenAI work and how it can be used responsibly in education.

After following this e-module, you will be able to:

- Explain how GenAI and Large Language Models (LLMs) work;
- Recognise the opportunities, limitations and ethical issues associated with GenAI;
- Identify ways in which you can use GenAI responsibly.

It will take you **approximately 45-60 minutes** to complete the whole e-module. You can choose whether you want to work your way through the material chronologically or move back and forth between chapters.

Figure 6: Screenshot of GenAI Module.

4 R&D Lab

Over the past year, we have grown a development team that actively contributes to AI-driven innovations in education. Our main focus this year was the first pilot version of our course chatbot, but we also developed several other tools, which we will elaborate on further.

4.1 Course Chatbot

Over the past year, we developed the *tilburg.ai* Course Chatbot—an AI-powered tool designed to help students engage more effectively with their course materials. Using Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), the chatbot delivers context-aware responses based on uploaded course content, ensuring that answers are accurate, transparent, and aligned with the curriculum. In conversations with similar initiatives at other Dutch universities, our team has emerged as a leader in this technology.

The chatbot is directly linked to course materials provided by instructors. Teachers can upload PDF versions of course syllabi, lecture slides, academic papers, and other relevant documents, creating a knowledge base for the system to reference to. When students start a chat, the chatbot first retrieves relevant excerpts from these materials. Subsequently, it uses large language models (LLMs) via the API of OpenAI, combining AI-generated content with the retrieved course materials. We host this application on a Kubernetes Cluster in our own Microsoft Azure environment. While the tool is fully functional, a broader rollout to students is still pending due to infrastructure constraints.⁶

Screenshots of the chatbot's desktop and mobile versions are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Screenshots of the desktop and mobile version of our Chatbot.

⁶ Per a POW decision (October 2024) and in collaboration with TUNEDIN, LIS is set to deliver the required infrastructure by Q1 2025 to migrate the chatbot from *tilburg.ai*'s Azure environment to the university's own—improving compliance and reducing costs. Until then, large-scale rollout remains on hold.

4.1.1 Pilot phase 1 (block 1, 2024/2025)

In phase 1 of the pilot (“1st block, 2024/2025), we started with seven courses, as depicted in Table 4.

This initial phase provided valuable insights into both the technical performance and user experience of the chatbot. During a tutorial session with the Arrest Helper with 50 students, in collaboration with the TSB innovation team, we observed that the chatbot became temporarily overloaded due to the simultaneous usage. We resolved the issue on the spot, which led us to implement automated server scaling based on real-time user load which was an important improvement in the stability of the system.

Additionally, while students appreciated seeing the sources of the chatbot’s answers, they indicated that having a built-in PDF viewer would improve their experience. Based on this feedback, we integrated a viewer into the next version of the application, making it easier to view source material directly within the chatbot.

Students also reported frustration about losing their chat history after closing their browser. To address this, we introduced a login system in the current version, allowing users to return to ongoing conversations across sessions.

Course Name	Contact person / teacher	Students	School
Online Data Collection and Management	Hannes Datta	30	TiSEM
Data Prep. and Workflow Management	Hannes Datta	30	TiSEM
Pedagogiek & diagnostiek	Marijn Gijzen	30	TSHD
E-business	Francesco Lelli	30	TiSEM
Arrest Helper	Eefje Ernst	50	TLS
Regeren & Besturen	Annelieke Mooij	60	TLS
Thesis begeleider	Annelieke Mooij	30	TLS

Table 4: Overview of participants first version course chatbot

4.1.2 Pilot phase 2 (block 2, 2024/2025)

In phase 2 (Block 2, academic year 2024/2025), we scaled up significantly by integrating chatbots into 22 additional courses across multiple schools and launched our first inter-university collaboration with a pilot at TU Eindhoven. Participating courses are shown in Table 5.

Course Name	Contact person / teacher	School
Asset Allocation & Sustainable Investing	Lieven Baele	TiSEM
Accounting For Economists	Wim Maas	TiSEM
Business Process Integration	Francesco Lelli	TiSEM
Data Analytics for Non-Life Insurance	Erwin Charlier	TiSEM
Data Science for Economists	Jan Boone	TiSEM
Diagnostiek	Nessa Ikani	TSB
Data Preparation & Workflow Management	Hannes Datta	TiSEM
Entrepreneurship & Business Innovation	Wynand Bodewes	TiSEM
Fixed Income Analysis	Frank de Jong	TiSEM
Finance For Economics & Business Economics	Fatemeh Hosseini Tash	TiSEM
Financial Market Infrastructures & Payments	Ron Berndsen	TiSEM
Marketing Management	Anick Bosman	TiSEM
Online Data Collection & Management	Hannes Datta	TiSEM
Organisatie & Strategie	Miranda Stienstra	TiSEM
Programming For Economists	Jan Boone	TiSEM
Strategy Analytics	Anindya Ghosh	TiSEM
Thinking & Deciding	Rianne Conijn	TU/E
Venture Design	Wynand Bodewes	TiSEM

Table 5: Overview of participants second evaluation phase of the course chatbot.

This phase taught us several important lessons:

1. We discovered that teachers frequently update their materials during the course. In practice, this meant that a manual handover via Matthijs was required to keep the chatbot content up to date. To reduce this dependency and streamline the process, we built a self-service platform where educators can upload and manage their course content directly (see Figure 10).
2. We expanded beyond student use and started developing chatbots for employees (Table 6). For instance, we built a bot for HR advisors to answer questions about the university's collective labor agreement (CAO), and another for program coordinators in the IBA program, using intranet content to handle frequently asked questions from students. This helped us refine and adapt our meta prompt to suit diverse audiences and organizational needs.
3. Initially, we created an internal dashboard to monitor application usage, but we soon realized its value for teachers and users as well. Given the rising debate around the environmental impact of AI, we aim to be as transparent as possible. In our next version, we will implement an *energy dashboard* that shows users an estimate of the energy consumed per interaction.
4. Several teachers expressed the wish to see what kinds of questions students ask the chatbot, and which topics are most frequently discussed. This can help

identify gaps or ambiguities in the course material and offer teachers new insights into how students engage with the content. In response, we will start building a *teacher dashboard* that provides topic-level analytics based on user interactions.

We also would like to quantitatively analyze usage data from our course chatbots. Jorna Leenheer (TiSEM) is preparing a study based on our collected data to provide a thorough analysis of how students interact with chatbots within a course setting. Moving forward, the evaluation of chatbot usage and output quality will play a larger role in our project planning for the coming year.

Specific chatbots	Contact person / Teacher	School
Arrest Assistant	Eefje Ernst	TLS
CV helper	Joyce Steenoven-Ladenstein	Career Services
Chatbot for IBA program coordinators	Anouk Jonkman	TiSEM
HR CAO chatbot	Stefan van der Meer	HR
Coaching pool chatbot	Stefan van der Meer	HR
Matching tool IBA/ECO	Bart Dormans	TiSEM

Table 6: “Special” chatbots, developed for use for programs or other divisions.

4.1.3 R&D phase (block 3, 2024/2025)

Based on our experiences and conversations with both students and faculty, we gathered insights to improve the next version of the chatbot. We have addressed the following issues in block 3 (2024/2025):

1. Implementing a login functionality to restrict access and ensure only authorized users can use the chatbot (i.e., Tilburg University students and staff).
2. Adding memory capabilities so the chatbot can retain context from previous interactions within a conversation (i.e., students can now view previous chats).
3. Enabling teachers to upload documents themselves and create course-specific chatbots, such as a chatbot focused on week 1 materials that can be shared with students (i.e., what used to be single chatbots has now evolved into a self-service chatbot platform).
4. Integrated the chatbot within Canvas (i.e., upon approval of course coordinators, course material can be automatically added to our bots, saving teachers time in setting up these bots).

We are now finalizing the last components of the platform. The remaining step before launch is migrating our Azure environment to the LIS Azure environment to ensure full integration within the university’s IT infrastructure (see also Policy & AI infrastructure). At 3 April, we got approval by LIS to start this migration, and currently await further instructions on how to proceed.

In Figure 8, we show a screenshot of the new (public) landing page of the chatbot platform. In Figure 10 and Figure 11, we depict screenshots that illustrate how teachers can create their own chatbots and share them with students.

Figure 8: Screenshot of Chatbot landing page (public)

Figure 9: Screenshot of Chatbot, illustrating the feature that teachers can now manage and share multiple chatbots with students.

Create new chatbot

Bot Title:

Welcome Message:

Starter Questions:

Select Files:

As part of which course would you like to make this chatbot?

Figure 10: Screenshot of Chatbot, illustrating how teachers can now create new chatbots.

4.2 Presentation-to-Video Converter (prototype)

We have developed a tool that automates the creation of web clips, addressing a major challenge for educators. Recording and maintaining web clips is both time-consuming and costly, yet the demand for online lectures continues to grow, especially with the reduction of physical lecture spaces at the university. To support this shift, we are currently testing a tool that can automatically generate web clips from PowerPoint presentations in three steps:

1. The teacher adds notes to the PowerPoint slides.
2. The tool extracts these notes and converts them into AI-generated speech.
3. A video is created, combining the slides with the AI-generated narration, which can then be downloaded and shared.

We added a screenshot of the user interface of this tool in Figure 11.

Presentation-to-Video

Upload Your PowerPoint

Select a **.pptx** file to convert your presentation to video.

The screenshot shows a web interface for converting a PowerPoint presentation to a video. At the top, it says "Presentation-to-Video" and "Upload Your PowerPoint". Below that, it instructs the user to "Select a .pptx file to convert your presentation to video." The main interface is a light gray box containing a "Choose a voice:" section with two radio buttons: "Free Voice" (selected) and "Paid Voice". Each has a "Listen" link. Below this is a file selection area with a button "Bestand kiezen" and a text field "Geen bestand gekozen". A large blue button "Upload & Process" is at the bottom of the main box. Below the main box is a dark gray button "View Your Upload History". At the very bottom, a black footer bar contains the text "Copyright © 2025 - Tilburg University, The Netherlands" and social media icons for Instagram and LinkedIn.

Figure 11: Screenshot of presentation-to-video tool developed by tilburg.ai.

4.2.1 Pilot phase

We have completed the tool in March 2025, and are currently preparing for a pilot phase with selected teachers across Tilburg's schools.

The rollout plan could be as followed:

- **Free voice:** This is a standard, robotic-sounding AI voice based on open-source technology. It allows fast and cost-effective generation of web clips and is suitable for quick internal content creation.
- **Premium voice:** This version leverages Eleven Labs, a leading provider in hyper-text-to-speech. It generates professional, human-like audio and is particularly useful for public-facing or high-quality educational content.

To help users make an informed choice, the tool provides a sneak preview feature: after generating the video with the free voice, users can hear a short demo of how the premium voice would sound.

Costs for the premium voice depend on the length of the video.⁷ Future integration in faculty budgets or project funding may be explored depending on demand and usage statistics.

⁷ E.g., 1-minute video: €0.43 (€0.28 for voice + €0.15 for server time). 60-minute video: €25.80 (€16.80 for voice + €9.00 for server time).

We believe this tool can offer a cost-effective and scalable alternative to recording videos in a traditional way. Our solution may complement existing solutions available at Tilburg University (such as the Studio, for producing high-end content), such as by enabling quick updates, microlearning modules, and support for hybrid teaching formats.

4.2.2 Next steps

Our initial focus was converting PowerPoint presentations into videos with AI-generated speech. However, our goal is to develop a fully automated web clip creation tool that will make the process seamless for educators.

In the ideal workflow, the tool would function as follows:

1. The teacher uploads materials (e.g., lecture notes, articles, or key concepts).
2. A PowerPoint is automatically generated, with an interface allowing the teacher to review and edit the slides.
3. An AI-generated script is created based on the PowerPoint, which the teacher can manually refine if needed.
4. A complete web clip is generated, with AI-powered voice-over, ready for use in online education.

To visualize this concept, we have created an initial sketch of the tool's design and functionality, as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Mock-up of AI presentation assistant.

4.3 Oral Assessment Tool (early prototype)

Oral assessments can serve as a valuable complement to written examinations. However, they are often not scalable, as they typically require the presence of a single teacher to ensure consistency—or risk reduced reliability when multiple graders are involved. To address this challenge, we envisioned conducting oral assessments using AI.

We recognize that this is an early-stage prototype, developed for a very specific setting and not yet tested with students. Still, the tool works, and developing it marked an important step forward. Beyond oral assessments, the underlying technology—speech recognition and voice output in our own environment—can also be used to power voice assistants for students, provide structured feedback, enable interactive AI-driven Q&As, or even create dynamic podcast-style formats. Taken together, these applications demonstrate the technical feasibility of building new forms of assessment and interactive learning experiences.

In this particular prototype, we focused specifically on the context of oral examination. The process works as follows:

1. We initialized our bot with course content (in particular, a research paper); we also built in a series of three questions that students would have to answer, and also explicitly created “hints” for each questions, in the case students would request them.
2. The student engages in a conversation with the bot, answering questions in an interactive format.
3. Students can orally request a hint, guiding them back on track if needed.
4. The session ends after three minutes in this pilot, and a transcript of the conversation is saved for the teacher for review.

We depict a screenshot of the early prototype in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Screenshot of an early prototype of tilburg.ai’s oral assessment bot (can also be used for interactive podcasts, etc.).

We are now in the process of setting up a second R&D wave, in which we want to involve Tilburg University’s assessment specialists to evaluate the tool’s usability and effectiveness. We also propose involving e-assessment, to learn from the experience of testing at scale.

After this R&D wave, we propose setting up a pilot phase in a formative setting, allowing students to practice course materials throughout the course rather than as part of an official exam. Once we gain more experience with the technology and receive further feedback from students and teachers, we can explore the possibility of testing it in a real-life, summative setting.

4.4 Tools for other TiU stakeholders

Over the past year, we have received numerous requests from outside the educational domain and have successfully collaborated on several AI-driven projects. These

initiatives demonstrate the broader applicability of our expertise, tool stack, and the potential for AI to streamline various university processes.⁸

- **CV-Checker** – Developed in collaboration with Career Services, this tool allows students to upload their CVs and receive instant AI-generated feedback, available 24/7.
- **HR Advisor Chatbot** – In collaboration with HR services, we designed a chatbot to support HR processes. The bot provides instant answers based on the university’s collective labor agreement (CAO), improving efficiency for both staff and HR professionals.
- **Support Chatbot for IBA Program Coordinators** – Together with the IBA program coordinators, we developed a chatbot to assist them with answering frequently asked student questions, using uploaded intranet data as a reference.
- **Matching Tool for IBA & ECO (Work in Progress)** – We are developing a Matching Tool for students applying to the IBA and ECO programs, replacing the traditional motivation letter with an interactive AI chatbot. Instead of evaluating students, the bot encourages them to reflect on their study choice by asking questions and providing informative answers about the programs. This creates a more engaging and personalized experience, helping students make informed decisions without offering any advice or selection outcome.

Our AI tools have demonstrated value not only in education but also across broader university operations. However, questions around budget allocation and time investment remain unresolved. When developing tools for other departments or divisions, it is often unclear whether the work should be covered by our existing budget or billed as a service.

Although we receive enthusiastic feedback from across the university, we are currently unable to guarantee long-term support—maintenance and ongoing development—due to the lack of structural funding for tilburg.ai beyond March 2026. This uncertainty limits the potential for deeper integration of our tools across the university.

⁸ See also the Appendix, for a list of tools and “problem owners”/initiators in the organization.

5 Budget

To kickstart Tilburg.ai, we received an initial investment of €360,000 from TiSEM at the start of 2024. This funding allowed us to hire a project manager, set up a team of research assistants, develop and test new AI tools, organize workshops, and build the tilburg.ai platform.

Total project expenditures to date are shown in Table 7.

Category	Description	Total (€)
Personnel Costs	Salaries of RA's, Project lead and project manager	€100.820
Material Costs	Hosting, compute, and storage for Tilburg.ai applications	€5,912
Total spent	Personnel costs + material costs	€106.732

Table 7: Total cost overview and budget usage in the first year.

Subsequently, we detail non-staff-related expenditures focusing on software tools, AI services, and infrastructure. These material costs play a crucial role in our project, especially given the pay-per-use structure of AI models and services. Expenses such as API tokens (e.g. OpenAI) and cloud infrastructure (e.g. Microsoft Azure) can scale depending on usage. As we continue to develop and expand our services, especially with the ambition to support AI applications university-wide, it is essential to monitor and manage these costs closely. This overview provides transparency into current expenditures and helps guide future decisions around scalability and sustainability.

The most significant expense was related to Microsoft Azure, which accounted for the largest portion of our total budget. This cost was notably higher because we operated using an individual Azure account, rather than integrating with Tilburg University's institutional Azure environment. Fortunately, we have now received agreement to transition into Tilburg University's Azure environment. Based on our conversations with LIS, this shift is expected to cut Azure-related costs significantly, resulting in an even more sustainable financial setup for future operations. A breakdown of all material costs is shown in Table 8.

Category	Description	Total (€)	Avg. Monthly (€)
OpenAI API tokens	AI models usage costs (converted from USD)	€548.63	€45.72
Microsoft Azure	Hosting, compute, and storage for Tilburg.ai applications	€2,330.16	€194.18
Subscriptions /other	ChatGPT licences and other AI tool subscriptions	€3,033.21	€252.77
Total spent	Sum of all material expenses	€5,912.00	€492.67

Table 8: Cost overview from material budget (licenses, tokens, hosting Azure)

6 Policy and IT Infrastructure

To ensure that Tilburg University can develop into a leading institution in the Netherlands in the field of AI, it is essential to focus not only on innovation but also on AI policy and infrastructure requirements. This is why AI policy and infrastructure form one of the core pillars of our approach.

6.1 IT-infrastructure at Tilburg University

To ensure that our AI tools go beyond pilot projects and become fully integrated within Tilburg University, we invested time this past year in drafting a memo on the desired AI infrastructure for the university. This effort was carried out closely with Janneke Kuipers (Information Manager at TunedIN) and Yvette Romans (AI Compliance Officer). The result was a proposal for an AI infrastructure, which was presented to the IT Architecture team at LIS for further discussion.

As illustrated in Figure 14, our proposal suggests connecting existing university systems to a Large Language Model (LLM). This approach would open the door for a wide range of innovations. For example, if an LLM is integrated with the Canvas environment, it would enable the development of our course chatbot. However, a proposed infrastructure plan is also essential for supporting researchers in their work.

Figure 14: "Future" AI-infrastructure, proposed

On November 29, 2024, we presented a migration plan to POW for transferring the AI applications developed under Tilburg.ai to Tilburg University's Microsoft Azure environment. This step is essential to ensure that our applications can be deployed university-wide.

Hosting these applications on Tilburg University's Azure environment would guarantee compliance with privacy and security regulations, as all data would remain internal and

be protected within Microsoft's secure infrastructure (including access to an “offline” copy of Chat GPT). Additionally, this move would result in significant cost savings since Tilburg University already has a contract with Microsoft, whereas tilburg.ai does not.

POW approved the plan, and we received approval from LIS to proceed with the migration. Concurrently, to pursue our ambition for providing AI tools to students safely, we initiated contact with SURF and, on March 25, 2025, met with the AI Hub to explore a potential collaboration. SURF proposed an AI infrastructure closely aligned with the vision we previously outlined internally, as depicted in Figure 15.⁹ We have also established links with a team similar to ours at the University of Amsterdam, and explored ways in which we can share core technology using open source principles.

Figure 15: Proposed AI-hub at SURF

6.2 Policy recommendations

At the end of the year, Yvette Roman was hired by TUNEDIN to lay the groundwork for Tilburg University's AI policy, specifically focusing on education. Throughout this process, Matthijs van Gils supported Yvette Roman wherever possible in drafting the document.

The AI policy memo is now under review by the exam committee, where Matthijs van Gils and Hannes Datta are actively involved to ensure that the policy aligns with the needs and expectations of all committee members. Jolanda Bachrach and more experts are revising the memo, with the goal of presenting a workable version to the vice deans and committee chairs by the end of week 13, 2025.

We regret that Yvette Roman has left Tilburg University at the end of March 2025. We have had a very fruitful and constructive relationship.

⁹ Under this model, SURF would host the Large Language Models (LLMs) along with the necessary compliance layer, while Tilburg University would access the models securely via an API key.

7 Grant Proposals

At the start of this project, we had not yet considered the potential role we could play in securing grants. However, as we developed the ability to design and implement AI-driven innovations in education, it became clear that our team could also be a valuable resource in writing and contributing to grant proposals. Over the past year, we have been involved in several grant applications—some of which we have already secured, while others are in the final evaluation stages.

7.1 EU grant – Erasmus: FLAIR (Fostering Learners AI readiness)

Budget: 40.000 per university (240k total)

Status: Secured

Applicants: Vienna University of Economics and Business, Ramon Llull University, University College Cork, University of Tartu, Yeditepe University and Tilburg University

Summary:

Objectives: What do you want to achieve by implementing the project?

The rapid public availability of generative AI tools has acted as a catalyst for changes in pedagogy and learning. The FLAIR project aims to prepare learners to thrive in a digitally transformed society by promoting the ethical and meaningful use of generative AI, ultimately fostering students' AI readiness.

Beyond supporting individual learners, FLAIR will provide valuable insights into the ongoing discourse on AI literacy in Europe, contribute to the advancement of AI literacy education, and promote transversal skills that are applicable across various disciplines.

Implementation: What activities are you going to implement?

The project will begin with comparative research on AI literacy frameworks, guidelines, and policies to gain an overview of different European approaches. Based on this research, two distinct approaches will be developed to help learners acquire the necessary skills to use generative AI responsibly and efficiently.

To support this goal, the project will create versatile and adaptable self-learning modules for students, along with transdisciplinary learning activities that can be seamlessly embedded into existing courses.

Results: What project results and other outcomes do you expect your project to have?

The research conducted in Phase 1 will result in a synthesis report that will serve as the foundation for an AI skills framework, identifying key transferable skills needed for AI literacy.

In Phase 2, the project will develop a blueprint and a comprehensive library of materials to help educators adapt the self-learning modules to their specific needs.

Finally, in Phase 3, the project will publish a toolkit for lecturers, focusing on AI-related skills that require facilitation. This will be complemented by learning nuggets designed to be easily integrated into courses across a range of disciplines.

7.2 Comenius leadership fellows (500.000 EUR, NRO)

Status: Awaiting decision on interview invitation (expected mid-April 2025)

Applicant: Hannes Datta (TiSEM)

Summary:

Tilburg University seeks to foster creativity to translate academic excellence into tangible societal impact. In a digital world, students' ability to make an impact arguably must extend into the digital space—such as by creating web or smartphone apps that address societal needs.

However, like many other higher education institutions, Tilburg University lacks the digital infrastructure to nurture this creativity. Virtual computing environments and security checks, for instance, are only accessible to select researchers. Additionally, app development is not yet part of the curriculum, though it could significantly enhance the digital skills of students enrolled in study programs across all of Tilburg University's schools. This gap is particularly concerning given the widespread rise of generative AI tools that make programming and app development more accessible. Yet, without proper digital infrastructure, students at Tilburg University cannot fully benefit from these advancements.

This project aims to create “Appify”, a platform that enables students to develop, test, and deploy their own apps. The platform will be supported by a curriculum designed to equip non-developers, particularly those in business, economics, psychology, and data science, with the necessary skills to create functional apps. To ensure the long-term viability of promising apps, students can join a coaching program to form student teams, operating as their own non-profit entity as they continue to roll out their apps. The project aims for a broad impact by making apps accessible online, sharing the curriculum with educational innovation teams nationally, and designing the platform for flexible onboarding of other institutions.

7.3 OS Large infrastructure (1.500.000 EUR, NWO/OpenScience NL)

Status: completed pre-proposal stage (4th out of 66); now preparing full proposal

Applicants: Hannes Datta (TiSEM), Ana Martinovici (Erasmus), and Tom Emery (Erasmus/ODISSEI), together with a team of researchers that are part of Tilburg Science Hub, as well as support staff (research software engineers)

Summary:

Despite the expanding adoption of open science, technical complexity, and insufficient documentation limit its implementation. For example, researchers often submit minimally documented data packages that fail to meet reproducibility standards. This project addresses this key challenge to adopting open science practices within the social sciences by expanding the accessible data management and documentation tools developed by the Tilburg Science Hub (TSH) and scaling them through integration with ODISSEI, the Dutch national research infrastructure for social sciences.

The project comprises four work packages: ReproBuddy, an AI-powered assistant for enhancing replication package quality; ReproRun, a secure computational environment for reproducibility certification using differential privacy; an expanded educational platform to support capacity-building; and OpenScienceRadar, a browser extension to increase journal policy transparency on open science. These components offer a solution to technical and documentation barriers, using open-source tools to deliver transparent, privacy-protected workflows. This project advances an inclusive, reproducible research ecosystem aligned with open science principles, expanding these capabilities across the social sciences, particularly for research with sensitive and secondary data.

8 Evaluation and next steps

In our first year, we made progress across all four focus areas: communication and outreach, AI literacy, the development of educational tools, and alignment with institutional infrastructure and policy. The following sections review what has been achieved and outline the proposed next steps for our second year.

8.1 Website, Social Media & Enhanced Reach

In the past year, we have made substantial progress in launching and growing the tilburg.ai website. The blog is now read by approximately 8,000 users each month. It features a wide range of content, including how-to articles, tutorials, and use cases.

We have also established a team of research assistants who curate and edit content, ensuring a steady flow of high-quality material. In addition, we have begun to activate a community of colleagues who contribute articles occasionally, reflecting the breadth of expertise across Tilburg University.

We will focus on the following next steps to continue our growth:

- We aim to increase integration of the website into all of TiSEM's educational programs. This can be achieved by engaging with academic directors and embedding tilburg.ai content into AI literacy initiatives, allowing it to be used organically within curricula.
- We intend to broaden content contributions from the TiSEM community by involving expert faculty members in writing about educational case studies and AI-related technologies. This can be organized via TAISIG, as well as through direct outreach to TiSEM faculty. We will also collaborate more closely with the University's Marketing & Communication team to align with institutional outreach and attract a broader audience.
- We will work with TiSEM staff to develop new AI-supported cases and assignments and make these available on tilburg.ai to share best practices and inspire broader adoption.

8.2 E-Learning and AI Literacy Initiatives

In the past year, we have supported the university-wide working group for AI in education by hosting self-guided learning modules on AI literacy, accessible via student.tilburg.ai and learn.tilburg.ai. In parallel, we have delivered over 30 workshops and presentations to faculty, support staff, and students, offering hands-on guidance on generative AI tools and their responsible use in education.

The coordination of AI literacy efforts was handed over to TunedIn, and we continue to contribute our technical expertise where relevant. In support of these efforts, Matthijs van Gils contributes to the international FLAIR grant on AI readiness, which enables the further expansion of literacy initiatives at Tilburg University.

We will focus on the following next steps in the next year:

- We will continue to provide technical support for the existing AI literacy modules, working closely with the university-wide working group on AI in education.
- We will contribute to the development of new AI literacy content, with a particular focus on the technical infrastructure. This could include an interactive (LLM-powered) learning module.
- For TiSEM specifically, we will support the integration of existing AI literacy materials into the school's educational programs.

8.3 R&D: Scaling Tools and Innovating Teaching

Over the past year, we have focused our R&D efforts on building practical AI tools that support teaching and learning. A key development has been the course chatbot, which helps students navigate course materials by answering questions with cited sources. After piloting the tool in 25 courses, we built a self-service platform that allows instructors to set up their own chatbot and share it with their students. The next step is to make this tool available across the university and support a wider rollout.¹⁰

Alongside these efforts, we experimented with new formats for learning, including a tool that turns slide presentations into narrated videos. This is planned for broader testing in the coming year. We also began early work on oral assessment. We also aimed to create our own prompt database. While we did not develop one in-house, we published several prompting tutorials on tilburg.ai and contributed to the development of a prompt database at Fontys at Mindlabs.

We will focus on the following next steps:

- We will roll out the course chatbot platform more broadly across campus so that all teachers and students can benefit from it and begin migration to the TiU Azure environment for compliance and scalability.
- We will extend the chatbot platform with a general-purpose mode — allowing use beyond individual courses and across various contexts. This version could be offered during TestVision exams to enable controlled, summative testing of LLMs in education.
- We will further develop the presentations-to-video tool, and evaluate how it could be offered more widely as a time-saving teaching support.

¹⁰ We also piloted a course search and recommendation tool based on the OSIRIS catalogue. As we could not find a suitable place to embed it, the tool has been retired for now but could be reactivated if interest arises.

- We will continue to pilot projects on automated grading, validation, and individualized assignments to explore how AI can support more adaptive and efficient learning experiences, while maintaining fairness, academic rigor, and compliance with the EU AI Act. In addition, we wish to a video-based AI learning platform – an interactive system where students can learn from existing videos from Panopto, with built-in AI tutors or quizzes.

8.4 Infrastructure and Policy Alignment

Over the past year, we have closely aligned our activities with Tilburg University's broader initiatives on AI in education. We coordinated regularly with TUNEDIN and contributed to university-wide documents on topics such as assessment and AI use. On the infrastructure side, we provided technical recommendations and worked with the CISO office and the university's privacy officer to ensure compliance with data protection standards. We also collaborated with Yvette Roman on AI policy development, contributing practical insights from our projects to help shape institutional guidelines.

We are now focusing on the following next steps:

- We seek to strengthen our technical infrastructure and fully migrate Tilburg.ai's tools and platforms to the university's official Azure cloud environment. This migration will improve security, support GDPR compliance, and enable better long-term scalability and support. We are working closely with LIS to implement this transition.
- As the university develops more formal guidelines for AI use, we will continue to contribute practical insights from pilot projects and tool development. Our aim is to help develop technical solutions to existing problems (e.g., summative assessment), that are not yet available for purchase commercially.
- We will continue providing input and technical guidance to LIS to help define and implement the IT infrastructure needed to support AI in education.

By integrating infrastructure and policy efforts, we hope to ensure that the AI tools developed at tilburg.ai can move beyond experimentation and become part of a sustainable, supported IT ecosystem at the university.

9 Beyond 2026: AI in education

Our objective beyond 2026 is to integrate Tilburg.ai as a permanent element within Tilburg University’s educational framework. We aim to transition from our current pilot phase into a long-term center that supports the development and maintenance of AI tools and serves as a resource for both teaching and applied research in AI.

9.1 Vision

Our vision is to transform tilburg.ai from a time-bound project into a permanent hub for educational innovation in AI.

With proper support and formal embedding within the university, tilburg.ai could become a center of innovation that continuously enhances teaching and learning with AI. This means not only sharing knowledge but also driving new AI tools, guiding policy on responsible AI use, and serving as a strategic advisor on AI in education.

In short, tilburg.ai can evolve into an integral part of Tilburg University’s strategy for the future – a go-to resource for faculty, students, and leadership on all matters related to AI in teaching and learning.

9.2 Formal Governance and Team

To support this long-term vision, we propose formalizing tilburg.ai as a permanent service unit with a clear governance structure and dedicated resources. This would allow the university to build and maintain capacity in a structured and sustainable way. The core development team would include roles such as a Software Engineer, Full-Stack Developer, Data Scientist, and RAG Engineer to develop and scale AI-driven educational tools. A Cloud Engineer (with MS Azure expertise) and a Solution Architect would help ensure technical alignment with the university’s broader IT infrastructure.

To support compliance and responsible use, additional roles such as an AI Governance Officer and an Information Manager are crucial. A project manager would coordinate daily operations, and a student team (including research assistants and interns) would continue to contribute to development, testing, and content creation.

Many of these capabilities already exist within the university. For example, the involvement of LIS staff—such as a Cloud Engineer and Solution Architect—could complement the tilburg.ai team. Building on these internal resources, we envision a flexible and multidisciplinary structure that supports responsible, effective integration of AI across education, research, and operations.

We also see value in continuing to collaborate beyond the university. Tilburg.ai is already involved in national-level discussions, such as through our contribution to the EdugenAI initiative led by the University of Amsterdam under the Npuls program. By

taking part in these and similar collaborations, we aim to help shape the broader ecosystem for AI in higher education in the Netherlands.

9.3 Exploring the potential for TIU's first student team

We see an opportunity to evolve our research assistant pool into Tilburg University's first official student team focused on AI innovation. In technical universities such as Eindhoven and Delft, student teams are integral to their innovation ecosystems. With the recent development of AI and data science programs at Tilburg University, there is a growing foundation to support such a team. If institutional support for [tilburg.ai](#) is secured, this team—guided by dedicated project leads and supported by paid research assistants—could offer valuable hands-on experience and further bolster the university's capacity for AI innovation. Preliminary interest from key stakeholders, such as Dirk van den Berg from KTO, highlights the potential for this initiative.

10 Appendix

Project Name	Initiated by	Status
Course Chatbot	Hannes Datta & Matthijs van Gils	Piloted, soon version 2
HR chatbot	Stefan van der Meer	Finished
IBA/ECO matching tool	Bart Dormans	MVP
IBA coordinators tool	Anouk Jonkman	Finished
Video-to-presenter	Herbert Hamers & Audrey de Louw	MVP
Oral assessment	T.B.A	MVP
CV-checker	Joyce van Steenoven-Ladenstein	Finished
Automated feedback	Tatiana Sokolova	MVP
Student team	Dirk van den Berg, KTO	Beginning phase
Learning from grants and communicating	Marieke Schoots	Beginning phase
Intranet AI search bar	Sandra Verhoeven-Klijn	Beginning phase
Intranet pop-up chatbot	Sandra Verhoeven-Klijn & Chris Eikelboom	Beginning phase
Tilburg Research Portal	Frank Diepmaat & Rianne Strijker- van Aspen	Beginning phase

Table 9: Overview of additional projects and their initiators.